
THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL INNOVATIVE TOOLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article reveals the impact of technology on teaching English , and shows how technology can help the process teaching and learning. The aim of the article is to show the importance of technology and to present the main points of teaching with technology. The use of technology has become an important of the learning process. Every language class usually uses some form of technology. Technology continues to help teachers facilitate language learning for their learners. Teachers should use educational innovative tools as projector, electronic whiteboards, Virtual Field Trips in order to explain more effectively end get satisfying results from learners. Using these tools help to enhance students` language skills , because it has a crucial role in developing their creativity and provides them with interesting, enjoyable and exciting alternatives to study the language.

Keywords: *educational innovative tool, projector, electronic whiteboards, Virtual Field Trips interactive smart boards*

Technology has had a significant impact on practically every part of our lives, including education. In many ways , education appears to have remained relatively unchanged over time. Looking at old photographs of classrooms , it is seen the scene extremely similar to the present classroom. Teacher is lecturing from the podium , while the students are sat with their books opened. Some students may be staring at the teacher, conversing with one another, or falling asleep. Modern classrooms are very similar. One distinction is that hardcover books have been replaced by screens of technological devices. This is not the only area where technology has made an impact. Teachers in the pre- technological age did not have many tools to enhance their teaching process . To make the learning process easy and enjoyable for learners, they relied mostly on the blackboard and chalk. Teachers, as the primary source of information, stood in the middle, delivering lectures to learners who listened

passively. In the modern era, however, classrooms shifted from being teacher-centered to being student-centered.

This resulted from a desire to focus more on the learners.

In a student-centered classroom, the learning responsibility is placed on the student with the goal of breaking them out of their shells and teaching them how to become self-sufficient. Teachers use a variety of technical tools at their disposal to try to make the learning process more efficient. [Boni Hamilton, 2015:75]

Technology transforms students from passive recipients to active learners and allows more profound and enriching linguistic immersion. Language learning has benefited from the usage of technology. Teachers can customize classroom activities with the use of technology, which improves the language learning process. Technology is becoming increasingly important as a tool to assist teachers in facilitating language acquisition for their students [Fahmy M.S., 1963:101]

When it is talked about technology in education, it means all types of technology that are used to enhance the learning experience. Here are most used technology tools in education.

- Electronic whiteboards
- Projectors
- Virtual Field Trips

Electronic whiteboards – in the digital age, static chalkboards and paper-based lessons don't connect with kids. Teachers who must rely on chalk to communicate with their students are condemned to fail. Students will tune out before the class begins if teachings are forced into lectures or written on chalkboards in the classroom. Students are encouraged to participate in the lessons via interactive smart boards. Teachers are not restricted in terms of what they can convey to students. In addition to traditional text-based training, movies, PowerPoint presentations, and graphics can be used. An interactive smart board, sometimes known as an electronic whiteboard, is a classroom technology that uses a digital projector to display graphics from a computer screen on a classroom board. A tool or even a student's finger can be used to "interact" with the graphics immediately on the screen by the teacher or a student. Interactive smart boards entice students to participate. An interactive smart board is also available. Teachers can access information from all over the world by connecting their computer to the internet or a local network. They can conduct a simple search and find a previous lesson they used. Suddenly, the teacher has access

to a variety of resources. The interactive white board is a significant benefit to both teachers and students in the classroom.

Modern technology can help increase the interaction in the teaching process, which is important for the development of communicative competence in a language.

Projector-With the introduction of projectors in the classroom, many teachers consider chalkboards to be almost obsolete. Rather than writing notes on the board, teachers might use projectors to display PowerPoint presentations, photographs, and even film as teaching resources. As a result, both teachers and students consider projectors to be effective classroom tools.

Projectors free teachers from the constraints of using chalk and dry-erase boards to communicate material to their students. Teachers can now use projectors to teach children about the world and places they have never seen or imagined by showing videos, slides, and photos. Students can listen to lectures delivered by international specialists. Teachers will also find the Internet more beneficial because projectors can display web content to an entire class instead of each student accessing information on a small individual PC. Many projectors also have excellent sound quality, which is useful while listening to music or watching nature films. Teachers had to spend time writing notes on the board and erasing material due to restricted space prior to the usage of projectors in the classroom. Projectors aid in the planning process, allowing lecturers to decide on lecture topic and key points ahead of time rather than making judgments on the fly. Projectors operate with the simple click of a button or mouse, saving up crucial class time. Teachers can more easily prepare all notes ahead to class for easy presentation by employing projectors. Teachers may also discover that they are spending less time repeating or rewriting knowledge that is now available with a single click.

Virtual field trips allow to explore environment through photographs, movies, audio samples, animations, and sounds. During the COVID-19 pandemic, educators were forced to discover new and innovative ways to provide material to their students. The virtual field trip has grown in popularity as a pedagogical method for linking young people to important educational experiences from the comfort and safety of their classroom — or home. Virtual field trips are not restricted by geography and are often less expensive than traditional in-person field visits. They minimize the need for transportation, save instructional time lost due to travel, and include less safety risks (no permission slips required). Furthermore, virtual field trips

provide meaningful, interactive experiences for students of all learning styles and expose them to a variety of perspectives.

Many teachers and educators work hard to find ways to improve learners' enthusiasm in learning. This idea can become a reality thanks to modern technologies. Teachers can use modern technology to incorporate photos, images, animations, and videos into their instructional materials, making learning more engaging. The simulated environment gives students an experience similar to the real experience. [Wang.X, Hana, 2019:56] As a result, it can draw students' attention and boost their participation in English learning.

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